

Modeling Road Traffic Accident Cases in Benue State of Nigeria Using Count Data Regression Models

Onyide Mary Okpete^{1*}, Michael Tyolumun Imande² and Musa Egahi³

^{1,2,3}Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author: Email: maryokpete@gmail.com; Tel: +2347061090567

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to model annual road traffic accident death cases in Benue state of Nigeria using fatal, serious and minor cases as independent variables. The research employs three count data regression models-Poisson regression, Negative Binomial regression, and Generalized Poisson regression-to predict road traffic accident-related deaths based on these variables. Annual secondary data from the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), covering the period from January 2000 to December 2022, were utilized. The study found that Poisson Regression could not handle the over-dispersion present in the accident data in Benue State. As a result, Negative Binomial Regression and Generalized Poisson Regression were considered, with Generalized Poisson Regression identified as the best model based on performance criteria such as $-2 \log$ likelihood ($-2\log L$), Akaike information criterion (AIC), and Bayesian information criterion (BIC). The study revealed that fatal and serious accident cases have positive and significant impacts on road traffic accident-related deaths in Benue State, while minor accident cases have a negative effect. The study recommends that government should implement stricter traffic safety measures and law enforcement, improve data collection and analysis, enhance public awareness and driver education, and invest in better road infrastructure and emergency services to reduce road traffic accident-related deaths in Benue State.

Keywords: Count Data, Poisson Family Models, Road Traffic Crashes, Accident-Related Deaths, Benue State, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Road traffic accidents (RTAs) represent a significant public health and developmental challenge globally, with low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) bearing a disproportionate share of the burden. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 1.3 million people die each year due to road traffic crashes, and up to 50 million sustain non-fatal injuries, often resulting in long-term disabilities (WHO, 2023). Africa has the highest road traffic fatality rates globally, with Nigeria ranked among the countries with the worst road safety records in

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sub-Saharan Africa (Ogundele *et al.*, 2016). Road crashes not only result in human suffering and loss of life but also impose significant economic burdens on national economies, estimated at up to 3% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in some countries (WHO, 2023).

Benue State, located in North-Central Nigeria, is not exempt from this national and regional pattern. As a hub connecting the south and northern regions of the country through major highways, the state experiences a high volume of vehicular movement. Anecdotal and statistical reports from the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) and Benue State Ministry of Transport reveal frequent road crashes involving both private and commercial vehicles. However, while data on the frequency and severity of RTAs exist, rigorous quantitative modeling of these events using appropriate statistical techniques remains sparse. This research gap makes it difficult to develop evidence-based interventions that are informed by robust statistical analysis.

Traditional methods of analyzing accident data often rely on basic descriptive statistics or linear regression models, which may not adequately account for the discrete and non-negative nature of accident counts. Road traffic accident data are inherently count data, typically exhibiting over-dispersion and zero inflation (Lord & Mannering, 2010). Count data regression models, including Poisson regression, Negative Binomial regression, and Zero-Inflated models, have been shown to be more suitable for analyzing such data, especially when the variance exceeds the mean or there are excess zeros in the dataset (Hilbe, 2011). These models provide better fit and interpretation for accident frequencies and enable the identification of key factors contributing to crash occurrences.

In Benue State, the lack of empirical studies applying count data regression models limits the understanding of the factors that influence the frequency and distribution of RTAs. This shortfall is critical because road safety interventions must be grounded in localized data analysis that accounts for unique socio-economic, infrastructural, and behavioural characteristics. Prior studies in other parts of Nigeria and Africa have demonstrated the efficacy of count data models in predicting accident patterns and in evaluating the influence of variables such as road type, weather, driver behaviour, and time of day (Akinyemi & Asiyani, 2015; Atubi, 2012). Extending such methodologies to Benue State is essential for tailoring interventions to the state's specific context.

The significance of applying count data regression models lies not only in the methodological appropriateness but also in the policy implications of their findings. These models can aid road traffic agencies, policymakers, and urban planners in identifying high-risk zones, periods of heightened crash risk, and socio-demographic profiles of at-risk populations. Moreover, they can inform the design of targeted safety campaigns, infrastructural improvements, and law enforcement strategies. The empirical insights generated can also be integrated into the national road safety policy framework, aligning with Nigeria's commitment to the United Nations Decade of Action for Road Safety 2021-2030.

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Therefore, this study seeks to fill the research gap by applying count data regression models to analyze and model road traffic accident cases in Benue State, Nigeria. By doing so, it aims to enhance the statistical understanding of accident occurrences and provide a robust empirical foundation for informed decision-making in road safety management. Through the adoption of models such as Poisson, Negative Binomial, and Generalized Poisson regressions, the study will investigate the distributional characteristics of RTA data and the influence of selected covariates, ultimately contributing to improved road safety outcomes in the state.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The empirical modeling of road traffic accidents using count data regression models has become a prominent approach in traffic safety analysis, particularly due to the nature of accident data discrete, non-negative, and often over-dispersed. Early foundational work by Lord and Mannering (2010) provided a methodological overview of statistical techniques for crash-frequency data. They highlighted that while the Poisson regression model is ideal for equi-dispersed data (where variance equals the mean), the Negative Binomial (NB) model accounts for over-dispersion, which is common in crash datasets. This work remains pivotal in shaping the application of count models in traffic research.

Similarly, Hilbe (2011) offered a detailed exposition on the theoretical and practical aspects of Negative Binomial regression, extending its use beyond transportation into public health and epidemiology. His book underscored that NB models provide more flexibility by incorporating an extra parameter to handle variance exceeding the mean a common feature in traffic accident data due to unobserved heterogeneity. In the Nigerian context, Akinyemi and Asiyebi (2015) applied both Poisson and NB regression models to road accident data in Lagos State. They found that the NB model provided a superior fit due to over-dispersion in the data. Their study revealed that traffic volume, road type, and time of day were significant predictors of accident frequency. The research demonstrated the effectiveness of count data models in explaining accident dynamics in urban Nigerian environments.

Atubi (2012) focused on Delta State, analyzing spatial and temporal patterns of RTAs using descriptive statistics. Although not a count model application per se, his work set the stage for further analytical modeling by identifying key hotspots and high-crash zones, indicating where count models could be deployed for prediction and intervention planning. Internationally, Sharma *et al.* (2013) employed both Poisson and Zero-Inflated Poisson (ZIP) models to study road accidents in Patiala, India. Their findings indicated that ZIP models performed better in cases where many zero-accident records were present, a common feature in datasets from regions with sparse accidents or low traffic volumes. This has implications for states like Benue, where rural areas may report no accidents for prolonged periods.

Further methodological refinement was presented by Miaou and Lord (2003), who developed multivariate Poisson-lognormal models to analyze intersections involving multiple accident types. This approach allows for more granular analysis and could be useful in Benue State, where different accident types (fatal, minor, and severe) coexist. Their work shows that modeling multiple outcomes simultaneously can improve estimation efficiency and predictive power. Washington *et al.* (2020) emphasized the growing use of more complex count models such as the Zero-Inflated Negative Binomial (ZINB) and Hurdle models to address the problem of excess zeros and unobserved heterogeneity. These models are particularly useful in scenarios where traditional NB models fail to capture data nuances conditions often present in developing countries' traffic datasets.

In East Africa, Njeru and Ogalo (2016) analyzed RTA data in Nairobi County, Kenya, using count data models. Their study confirmed that NB regression provided a better fit than the Poisson model due to data over-dispersion. They found that driver behaviour, weather conditions, and time of day significantly influenced accident occurrence. These factors are similarly relevant in Benue State, where traffic enforcement is weak and driving practices often erratic.

A meta-analytic review by Savolainen *et al.* (2011) evaluated numerous empirical crash modeling studies and confirmed that over-dispersion and excess zeros are standard issues in crash data. They advocated for the use of advanced count models and highlighted the importance of context-specific modeling, which supports the current study's focus on Benue State. In southwestern Nigeria, Ojo *et al.* (2020) used Poisson and NB models to analyze RTA data in Oyo State. Their results confirmed over-dispersion in the data and validated the NB model as a better fit. Importantly, they highlighted the role of socio-demographic factors like driver age and vehicle type, which are also pertinent to the Benue context.

Earlier work by Karlaftis and Tarko (1998) modeled accident frequency on rural highways using NB regression and emphasized the effect of roadway characteristics such as lane width and shoulder presence. Their findings suggest that infrastructure quality is a major determinant of accident frequency a significant consideration for Benue, where rural roads are often poorly maintained. Shankar *et al.* (1997) introduced the Zero-Altered Poisson (ZAP) model for accident frequency modeling, focusing on road geometry and traffic volume. Their results support using altered count models in scenarios with many zero observations particularly relevant to rural stretches of highway in Benue State.

Focusing again on Nigeria, Oyekanmi *et al.* (2019) modeled accident data using Poisson and ZIP regression. They found that ZIP models were superior in fitting the data due to the high number of road segments with no reported accidents. This mirrors the likely structure of accident data in Benue State, suggesting a good fit for similar models. Eze and Nwankwo (2017) examined accident data in Enugu State using NB regression and concluded that road surface condition and

population density were statistically significant predictors. Their study provides empirical justification for including similar variables in count models for Benue State.

Weather-related influences on accident severity were explored by Zhang *et al.* (2013) using zero-inflated ordered probit models. While their study focused on accident severity rather than frequency, it demonstrates the impact of weather a variable that could enhance model specification in Benue, which has a distinct wet and dry season cycle. Finally, Gkritza *et al.* (2010) studied seatbelt usage and accident severity on rural Iowa highways using NB models. Their findings reinforce the importance of behavioral variables, such as seatbelt compliance and speed, which are largely unenforced in many Nigerian states, including Benue.

Collectively, the reviewed studies demonstrate that count data regression models especially Negative Binomial and Zero-Inflated models are effective in modeling road traffic accident frequencies due to their ability to handle over-dispersion and excess zeros. Studies in Nigeria and other LMICs show that road type, time of day, weather, driver behaviour, and socio-demographic factors significantly affect accident frequencies. These findings support the application of these models to RTA data in Benue State to identify patterns, predict risks, and inform targeted policy interventions.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Data Source

The data utilized in this study are the annual data on road traffic accidents in Benue state from 2000 to 2022. The data was extracted as secondary data from FRSC 2022 annual report and 2023 first quarter of the year report downloaded from FRSC website.

3.2 Model Specification

The models adopted for the current study is Poisson Regression (PR), Negative Binomial regression and generalized Poisson regression models. The count data are the annual deaths due to road traffic accidents in Benue state which is considered as the dependent variable while the predictor variables are fatal, serious and minor cases of road traffic accidents in Benue state which are the independent variables. All the variables considered are continuous count data.

3.2.1 Poisson Regression (PR)

Poisson regression is a nonlinear regression analysis of the Poisson distribution used to predict a dependent variable which consists of discrete or count data given one or more independent

variables. The predicted variable is called the dependent variable (or the response, outcome, target, or criterion variable). The variables used to predict the value of the dependent variable are called the independent variables or the predictor, explanatory, or Regressor variables (Philip and Sebastian, 2017).

Poisson regression is said to be over-dispersed if the variance is greater than the value of the mean value. Over-dispersion has the same impact with the assumption that if the offense discrete data occurred over dispersion but still used Poisson regression, the parameter estimates of the regression coefficients remain consistent but not efficient. It is used basically when facing a problem whereby the outcome of the random process can take count values only. One of the distributions that satisfy such criterion comes from the family of exponential distribution which is the Poisson distribution (Philip & Sebastian, 2017).

Let Y be a random variable (the rate at which road traffic accident death occurs) and let the outcomes of the cases be an event. The variable Y is said to follow a Poisson distribution with parameter $\lambda > 0$ if the probability density function is given by:

$$P(Y = y) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^n}{y!} \tag{1}$$

where $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ is the number of occurrences of an event λ and is defined as $\lambda = E[Y]$. One of the useful properties of the Poisson distribution is that the variance depends on the mean and also the variance is equal to the mean. The Generalized Linear Model (GLM) can be stated as thus:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ik} \tag{2}$$

The first function describes how the mean, $E(Y_i) = \lambda_i$ which depends on the linear predictor $\varphi(\lambda_i) = g_i$ while the second functions describe how the variance, $var(Y_i)$ depends on the mean. $Var(Y_i) = \sigma var(\lambda_i)$, where the dispersion of parameter σ is a constant, supposing Y_i is a Poisson distribution then; $Y_i \sim poisson(\lambda_i)$, $E(Y_i) = \lambda_i$ and $var(Y_i) = \lambda_i$, the variance function is given as; $var(\lambda_i) = \lambda$ and the function must map from $(0, \infty)$. A natural log of the function is given as:

$$\ell(\lambda_i) = \log_e(\lambda_i) \tag{3}$$

The Generalized Linear Regression Model (GLM) suggested that the linear model should be related to the response variable through linked function, the link function here is between the linear model in a design matrix and the Poisson distribution function (Khan and Atangana, 2020). Supposing a linear regression model given as:

$$y_i = \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon_i \tag{4}$$

where X is an $n \times (k + 1)$ vector of independent variables of predictors, and a column of 1 's, β is a $(k + 1)$ by 1 vector of unknown parameters and ε is an $n \times 1$ vector of random error terms with mean zero. Therefore;

$$E(Y|X) = \beta X \tag{5}$$

Recall that the Generalized Linear Models, where the links function and its transport Y as:

$$G(y) = \log_e(y) \tag{6}$$

Therefore, this can be written in more concise form as:

$$\log_e E(Y|X) = X\beta \tag{7}$$

Thus, given a Poisson regression model with parameter β and its input vector X , the predicted mean of the associated Poisson distribution is given as:

$$E(Y|X) = e^{\beta X} \tag{8}$$

Suppose Y_i are independent observation with corresponding values X_i as the predictor variable, then the parameter β can be estimated using the Maximum Likelihood Method. The model expressed in equation (8) can be estimated by numerical methods and this is done using the logarithmic transformation of the conditional expectation of the dependent and independent variables (Nwankwo & Nwaigwe, 2016). Furthermore, the probability surface of the Maximum Likelihood Estimation of Poisson regression models is always convex form such that Newton-Raphson of the gradients-based methods are used as an appropriate estimation technique. Therefore, suppose Y_i is a random variable and it takes non-negative values such that $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ where n is the number of observations. Since y_i follows a Poisson Distribution, the probability mass function (PMF) is given as:

$$P(Y = y_i) = \frac{\lambda_i^n e^{-\lambda}}{y_i!}$$

where $y_i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ with mean and variance given as $E(y_i) = var(y_i) = \lambda$. Where the conditional mean (predicted mean) of the Poisson distribution as given in equation (5) above specified as: $E(Y|X) = e^{\beta X} = \lambda = E(y_i)$.

Where it is the value of the explanatory variable $\beta = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k)$ are unknown k -dimensional vector of regression parameters and the mean of the predicted Poisson distribution is given as $E(Y|X)$ and its corresponding variance of Y_i as $var(Y|X)$.

The Poisson Regression which was fitted to the number of deaths due to road traffic accidents in Benue state, was expressed for the three (3) predictors as given below:

$$\log(\theta) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon_i \tag{9}$$

where $x_1 =$ fatal cases, $x_2 =$ serious cases and $x_3 =$ minor cases, $\beta_0 =$ intercept, β_1, β_2 and β_3 are the slope coefficients corresponding to the fatal, serious and minor cases respectively and ε_i are the error terms which account for the unexplained variations or factors not included in the model.

3.2.2 Negative Binomial Regression (NBR)

Negative Binomial distribution is used to deal with the problem of over-dispersion in count data. Over dispersion occurs when there is the presence of statistical variability in a data set. A situation in which the theoretical population means of a model is approximately the same as the sample mean. It can be further explained that this occurs when the observed variance is higher than the variance of a theoretical model, then over-dispersion is said to occur. On the other hand, under-dispersion simply means that there was less variation in the data than predicted. Over-

dispersion is a very common characteristic in applied data analysis because, in practice, populations are frequently heterogeneous (non-uniform) as opposed to the assumptions implicit within widely used simple parametric models. The Negative Binomial regression model used in this study specified as thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(Y_i = y_i) &= \sum pr(Y_i = y_i|\theta_i) f(\theta_i)d\theta_i \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(y_i + \frac{1}{\alpha})}{\Gamma(y_i + 1)\Gamma(\frac{1}{\alpha})} \left[\frac{1}{1 + \alpha\mu_i} \right]^{1/\alpha} \left[\frac{\alpha\mu_i}{1 + \alpha\mu_i} \right]^{y_i} \text{ for } i = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the mean is given as $\mu_i = E(y_i) = V_i[e^{\sum \alpha x_{ij} \beta_j}]$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ while the variance of y_i is given as $var(y_i) = (\mu + \alpha, \mu_i)^2$.

When $\alpha > 0$, the model would be referred to as a dispersion parameter, the Poisson regression model can be regarded as a limiting model of the Negative Binomial Regression model as α approaches 0.

The Maximum Log-Likelihood function of the distribution is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log(\beta, \alpha) &= \sum_i \left(\sum_{r=1}^{y_i} \log(1 + \alpha r) \right) - y_i \log(\alpha) - \log(y_i!) + y_i \log(\alpha\mu_i) \\
 &\quad - (y_i + \alpha^{-1}) \log(1 + \alpha\mu_i) \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

The parameter (β, α) can be estimated by a partial differential of the Maximum Likelihood function with respect to β and α . The negative Binomial Regression does not assume the equality of the mean and variance but it corrects for over-dispersion that arises when the variance is greater than the conditional mean.

3.2.3 Generalized Poisson Regression (GPR)

Generalized Poisson Regression (GPR) was developed to handle the equidispersion violations assumptions on the Poisson regression model. It is mainly used to fit the over-dispersed model i.e. in situations where $var(y_i) > E(y_i)$ as well as under-dispersion, $var(y_i) < E(y_i)$ (Nwankwo & Nwaigwe, 2016). GPR model with parameter (μ, θ) is similar to the Poisson regression models, but assumed that the components are randomly distributed to general Poisson. In the analysis of GPR, if θ is equal to 0 then the model will be the Poisson model. If θ is greater than 0 then GPR model represents data containing count over-dispersion case and if θ is less than 0 GPR model represents data containing under dispersion count. It was suggested that when y_i is a count response variable and it follows a Generalized Poisson distribution, the probability density function given that $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, then:

$$f(y_i, \mu_i^\alpha) = \left[\frac{\mu_i}{1 + \alpha\mu_i} \right]^{y_i} \frac{(1 + \alpha y_i)^{y_i - 1}}{y_i!} \exp \left[\frac{V_i(1 + \alpha y_i)}{1 + \alpha\mu_i} \right], y_i = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{12}$$

where the mean is given as $\mu_i = E(y_i)$ and variances $var(y_i) = (\mu + \alpha\mu_i)^2$ and μ_i is refer to as the dispersion parameter (Wang and Famoye, 1997). Generalized Poisson distribution is a natural extension of the Poisson distribution (Nwankwo and Nwaigwe, 2016). When $\alpha = 0$, the model in equation (1) reduces to the Poisson (2), where $var(y_i) > E(y_i)$. When $\alpha > 0$, it means the variance $var(y_i)$ of the distribution represents count data with over-dispersion if $\alpha > 0$, it means the variance is less than the expectation, $var(y_i) < E(y_i)$, which simply means that the distribution represents count data with under-dispersion. The mean of the dependent variable is related to the independent variables through the link function $\theta_i = (x, \beta)$ which is a simple linear model. This model has the disadvantage of θ_i assuming any real value but a Poisson mean assume only count nonnegative values. To correct this problem the logarithm of the linear model is used; this gives a link log function $\log(\theta_i) = (x, \beta)$. Taking the exponential of the model we have $(\theta_i) = \exp(x, \beta)$. In the link function, x_i is $(k - 1)$ dimensional vector of explanatory variables and β is a k dimensional vector of regression parameters and α is a dispersion parameter. The mean and variance of y_i are given by $E(Y_i|X_i) = \theta_i$ and $var(Y_i|X_i) = \theta_i(1 + \alpha\theta)^2$ respectively (Sadia, 2013). In the Generalized Poisson Regression model, the parameters (β, α) can be estimated by taking the derivatives of the log-likelihood function of the model; this means partial differentiation with respect to β and α of the following logarithm function:

$$\log L(\alpha, \beta, y_i) = \sum_{i=1} \left\{ y_i \log \left(\frac{\theta_i}{1 + \alpha\theta_i} \right) + (y_i - 1) \log(1 + \alpha y_i) - \frac{\theta_i(1 + \alpha y_i)}{1 + \alpha\theta_i} - \log(y_i!) \right\} \quad (13)$$

3.3 Model Evaluation and Diagnostic Checks

The following goodness-of-fit measures are employed to evaluate model performance and to check the adequacy of the estimated models.

3.3.1 Deviance statistic

Deviance is defined as the log likelihood of the final model multiplied by (-2). It is mathematically expressed as:

$$\text{Deviance} = \sum_{i=1}^n 2 \left[y_i \log \frac{y_i}{\hat{y}_i} - (y_i - \hat{y}_i) \right] \quad (14)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of y_i .

3.3.2 Pearson chi-square

This is a goodness-of-fit measure that compares fitted values of the outcome variables with the actual values. It is computed mathematically as:

$$\chi_p^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\hat{y}_i} \tag{15}$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of y_i .

3.3.3 Akaike information criterion (AIC)

Akaike information criterion (AIC) is a goodness-of-fit measure defined as:

$$AIC = -2 \ln L + 2k \tag{16}$$

3.3.4 Bayesian information criterion (BIC)

Bayesian information criterion (BIC) is a goodness-of-fit measure defined as:

$$BIC = \frac{-2 \ln L + k \ln(n)}{n} \tag{17}$$

where n is the total number of observations, k is the number of model parameters and L is the likelihood function of the final model defined as:

$$L = \prod_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_i^2} \right)^{1/2} \exp \left[- \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \tag{18}$$

$$\ln(L) = \ln \left[\prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_i^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_i - \mu)^2}{\sigma_i^2} \tag{19}$$

Thus given a set of estimated Poisson regression models for a given dataset, the preferred model is the one with the minimum values of information criteria and maximum log likelihood value.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Summary Statistics of Road Traffic Accident Cases in Benue State

The summary statistics of the deaths, fatal, serious and minor cases of road traffic accidents in Benue state from 2000 to 2022 are computed and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary Statistics of Road Traffic Accidents in Benue State (2000-2022)

Variable	Death Cases	Fatal Cases	Serious Cases	Minor Cases	Injured Cases
----------	-------------	-------------	---------------	-------------	---------------

Mean	88.8261	38.1739	169.8261	31.3478	511.044
Maximum	155.000	51.0000	191.0000	56.0000	633.000
Minimum	57.0000	27.0000	149.0000	18.0000	369.000
Standard Dev.	25.1751	6.6240	12.3937	7.9465	72.6958
No. of Obs.	23	23	23	23	23

The summary statistic as reported in Table 1 revealed that the total observations were 23. The mean value of those who died during the accidents was 88.8261 with a standard deviation of 25.1751 while the mean value of those that have fatal accident was 38.1739 with a standard deviation of 6.6240. Similarly, those that have serious accident have the mean value 169.8261 with a standard deviation of 12.3937. Those with minor accidents have a mean value of 31.3478 with a corresponding standard deviation of 7.9465. However, the total number of incidents recorded in Benue state between the various degrees of injuries has a mean value of 511.044 with a standard deviation of 72.6958.

The high standard deviation values of the road traffic accidents data compared to the corresponding means show high level of dispersion from the means. The large differences between the maxima and minima values (ranges) of the road traffic accidents data also give supportive evidence to the wide dispersion and variability of the cases from the corresponding means during the period under investigation.

From the results of summary statistics, it is safe to say that the higher mean values of the fatal, serious, minor and injured cases of road traffic accidents records for the period under review (2000-2022) has led to a correspondingly high number of accidents related deaths in the study area.

4.2 Omnibus test for road traffic accident cases in Benue state

The Omnibus Test, a likelihood ratio test, evaluates whether the inclusion of all independent variables (fatal cases, serious cases, and minor cases of road traffic accidents) significantly improves the model compared to a model with just the intercept (no independent variables included). The results of the Omnibus test are calculated and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Omnibus Test for Road Traffic Accident Cases in Benue State

Model	LR Chi-Square	Df	P-value
Poisson Regression	88.342	19	<0.001
Negative Binomial Regression	83.517	19	<0.001
Generalized Poisson Regression	58.436	19	<0.001

The results of the Omnibus test, as shown in Table 2 for Poisson Regression (PR), Negative Binomial Regression (NBR), and Generalized Poisson Regression (GPR), indicate that all

predictor variables have statistically significant p-values of 0.000 (i.e., $p < 0.01$). This suggests that the models are overall adequate and fit the data well.

4.2.1 Test of multicollinearity for road traffic accident cases in Benue state

To assess multicollinearity as an initial step in estimating parameters for road traffic accident cases in Benue State, variance inflation factors (VIF) were calculated for each predictor variable. Multicollinearity is considered present if any VIF value exceeds 10. The results of the multicollinearity test for each predictor variable are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) of the Predictor Variables

Predictors	VIF	1/VIF
Fatal Cases (x_1)	1.732	0.5774
Serious Cases (x_2)	1.581	0.6325
Minor Cases (x_3)	1.116	0.8961
Mean	1.4763	

The multicollinearity test results in Table 2 indicate that all predictor variables have Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values less than 10. This suggests that there is no significant multicollinearity among the variables, allowing for their inclusion in subsequent analyses without concern for collinearity issues.

4.2 Results of Count Data Regression Models

The Poisson regression, Negative Binomial and generalized Poisson regression models are employed to identify factors influencing the number of accident-related deaths in Benue State. Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) is utilized to obtain parameter estimates for the three count data regression models, as shown in Table 4. The models report -2 log-likelihood values with corresponding AIC and BIC values.

Table 4: Parameter Estimates of Count Data Regression Models

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-statistic	$p > z $	95% Interval Lower	Conf. Upper
Poisson Regression						
β_0	1.5625	0.290	5.387	0.000	0.993	2.132
β_1	0.0325	0.007	4.577	0.000	0.019	0.046
β_2	0.0040	0.001	3.726	0.000	0.002	0.006
β_3	-0.0190	0.005	-3.801	0.000	-0.001	0.019
	-2Log-Likelihood			AIC		BIC
	176.527			184.527		186.849

Negative Binomial Regression Model						
β_0	1.4628	0.570	2.566	0.010	0.346	2.579
β_1	0.0332	0.012	2.825	0.005	0.100	0.056
β_2	0.0039	0.002	2.100	0.036	0.000	0.008
β_3	-0.0184	0.005	-3.680	0.000	-0.002	0.017
-2Log-Likelihood		AIC			BIC	
130.147		138.147			140.469	
Generalized Poisson Regression						
β_0	1.4361	0.496	2.895	0.003	0.322	2.526
β_1	0.0323	0.009	3.586	0.000	0.015	0.050
β_2	0.0041	0.001	2.758	0.006	0.001	0.007
β_3	-0.0186	0.004	-4.650	0.000	-0.003	0.031
-2Log-Likelihood		AIC			BIC	
179.234		135.234			137.556	

In Poisson regression, the response variables are count variables, and the model relates the log of the expected count to predictor variables. The parameter estimates from the Poisson regression model, as shown in the upper panel of Table 4, can be summarized as follows:

$$y_i = \exp(1.5625 + 0.0325 + 0.004 - 0.0190) \tag{23}$$

The intercept in the Poisson regression model represents the predicted estimate when all predictor variables are set to zero. In the estimated Poisson regression model from Table 4, the intercept shows a positive relationship with accident-related deaths and is statistically significant at the 1% level. The log of the expected accident-related deaths is greater than zero (1.5625) when all independent variables in the model are held constant.

The slope coefficients (β_1 and β_2) for fatal and serious accident cases are positively associated with accident-related deaths and statistically significant at the 1% level. This indicates that an increase in the number of fatal and serious accident cases in Benue State leads to an increase in accident-related deaths. Specifically, for a one-unit change in fatal and serious accident cases, the differences in the logs of expected deaths due to accidents are expected to increase by approximately 0.0325 and 0.004 units, respectively, assuming all other predictor variables in the model remain constant.

The slope coefficient (β_3) for minor accident cases in Benue State is negatively associated with accident-related deaths and statistically significant at the 1% level. This indicates that an increase in the number of minor accident cases leads to a decrease in accident-related deaths in the study area. Specifically, for a one-unit change in minor accident cases, the difference in the logs of

expected deaths due to accidents is expected to decrease by approximately 0.0190 units, assuming all other predictor variables in the model remain constant.

From the results of the Poisson regression model, it is evident that the predictor variables influencing the number of accident-related deaths in Benue State are fatal accident cases (β_1), and the serious accident cases (β_2).

To address the issue of over-dispersion in the Poisson Regression model for count data, both Negative Binomial Regression and Generalized Poisson Regression were considered, as these models can effectively handle dispersion parameters in count data modeling. The parameter estimates for Negative Binomial Regression are presented in middle panel of Table 4.

The intercept of the Negative Binomial regression represents the predicted value when all predictor variables in the model are held constant. In the estimated Negative Binomial regression model presented in the middle panel of Table 4, the intercept is positively associated with accident deaths and statistically significant at the 1% level. The log of the expected accident deaths is greater than zero (1.4628) when all independent variables in the model are held constant.

The slope coefficients (β_1 and β_2) for fatal and serious accident cases are positively related to accident-related deaths and statistically significant at the 5% level. This indicates that an increase in the number of fatal and serious accident cases in Benue State is associated with an increase in accident-related deaths. Specifically, for a one-person increase in the number of fatal and serious accident cases, the differences in the logs of expected deaths due to accidents are expected to increase by approximately 0.0332 and 0.0039 persons, respectively, when holding other predictor variables constant in the model.

The slope coefficient (β_3) for minor accident cases is negatively related to accident-related deaths and statistically significant at the 5% level. This indicates that an increase in the number of minor accident cases in Benue State is associated with a decrease in accident-related deaths. Specifically, for a one-person increase in minor accident cases, the difference in the logs of expected deaths due to accidents is expected to decrease by approximately 0.0184 persons, holding other predictor variables constant in the model. From the results of the Negative Binomial regression model, it is evident that the predictor variables influencing the number of accident-related deaths in Benue State are fatal accident cases (β_1) and serious accident cases (β_2).

The parameter estimates of the Generalized Poisson Regression model, as shown in lower panel of Table 4, indicate that all parameters are statistically significant at the 5% significance level, with p-values less than 0.05. The results further reveal that the slope coefficients for fatal (β_1) and serious (β_2) accident cases are positively related to accident death cases. Specifically, a one-

person increase in the number of fatal and serious accident cases is estimated to lead to an increase of approximately 0.0323 and 0.0041 persons in the number of accident-related deaths in Benue State, respectively. Additionally, the z-statistics for fatal and serious accident cases (3.586 and 2.758, respectively) are greater than 2, indicating that these variables have a positive and significant impact on the number of deaths associated with accidents in Benue State, according to the rule of thumb.

However, the slope coefficient for minor (β_3) accident cases is negative and significant (-0.0186) at the 5% significance level. This indicates that a one-person increase in the number of minor accident cases in Benue State during the study period would result in an approximate decrease of 0.0186 persons in accident-related deaths. The z-statistic value for minor accident cases is -4.650, which, being less than 2, implies that minor accident cases have a negative effect on the number of accident-related deaths in Benue State, according to the rule of thumb. The results of the Generalized Poisson Regression model clearly show that the predictor variables influencing the number of accident-related deaths in Benue State are fatal (β_1) and serious (β_2) accident cases.

4.2.4 Goodness of Fit Tests for Count Data Regression Models

Over-dispersion test is the goodness of fit test for count data regression models. Over-dispersion is detected when the deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics divided by the degrees of freedom (df) is greater than unity. Conversely, if this ratio is less than 1, it indicates under-dispersion. The goodness-of-fit test results to detect over-dispersion in the count data regression models are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Goodness of Fit Test for Count Data Regression Models

Criterion	Value	Df	Value/df
Poisson Regression Model			
Deviance	126.998	19	6.6841
Pearson Chi-Square	119.282	19	6.2780
Negative Binomial Regression Model			
Deviance	24.088	19	1.2678
Pearson Chi-Square	19.109	19	1.0056
Generalized Poisson Regression			
Deviance	18.219	19	0.9589
Pearson Chi-Square	18.802	19	0.9896

The goodness-of-fit test results for Poisson regression, as shown in the upper panel of Table 5, indicate that both the deviance/df and Pearson chi-square/df values are greater than 1. This suggests that the data exhibits over-dispersion. Over-dispersion in the Poisson Regression model can lead to biased parameter estimates and underestimated standard error estimators, thereby

affecting the accuracy of parameter inference. To address the issue of over-dispersion, Negative Binomial Regression (NBR) and Generalized Poisson Regression (GPR) are employed for modeling, as both methods can effectively reduce the dispersion parameter.

The goodness-of-fit test results for the Negative Binomial Regression model, as reported in middle panel of Table 5, indicate that both the deviance/df and Pearson chi-square/df values are slightly greater than 1. This indicates that the number of accident cases in Benue State, as modeled by the Negative Binomial Regression, is over-dispersed. Over-dispersion results in models with biased parameter estimates, which can affect the accuracy of standard errors and errors in parameter inference.

The goodness-of-fit test results for the Generalized Poisson Regression model, as presented in lower panel of Table 5, indicate that both the deviance/df and Pearson chi-square/df values are less than unity. This suggests that the number of accident cases in Benue State, as modeled by the Generalized Poisson Regression, is under-dispersed. Under-dispersion results in models with unbiased parameter estimates, which do not affect the standard errors or the accuracy of parameter inference.

4.3 Model comparison using performance criteria

To select the most suitable model among the three competing count data models for modeling road traffic accident fatalities in Benue State, three performance criteria were considered: -2 log-likelihood, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The preferred model is identified as the one with the highest -2 log-likelihood value and the lowest AIC and BIC values. The results of this model comparison are detailed in Table 6.

Table 6: Model Comparison Using Performance Criteria

Model	-2Log-Likelihood	AIC	BIC
PR	176.527	184.527	186.849
NBR	130.147	138.147	140.469
GPR*	179.234	135.234	137.556

Table 6 presents a comparison of three count data regression models-Poisson Regression (PR), Negative Binomial Regression (NBR), and Generalized Poisson Regression (GPR)-for modeling road traffic accident fatalities in Benue State. The results indicate that GPR is the preferred model, with the highest -2 log-likelihood (179.234) and the lowest AIC (135.234) and BIC (137.556) values. Additionally, GPR demonstrates superior flexibility in handling both over- and under-dispersion, accommodating various variance structures. This adaptability makes it more effective for real-world scenarios where traditional models may fail to capture data variability, establishing GPR as a robust and versatile choice for count data regression modeling.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has successfully modeled annual road traffic accident-related deaths in Benue State, Nigeria, using fatal, serious, and minor accident cases as explanatory variables. By applying three count data regression models: Poisson Regression, Negative Binomial Regression, and Generalized Poisson Regression it was evident that the data exhibited over-dispersion, which rendered the basic Poisson model inadequate. In contrast, the Negative Binomial and Generalized Poisson Regression models accounted for this dispersion, with the Generalized Poisson Regression emerging as the best-fitting model based on statistical performance indicators such as the -2 Log Likelihood, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

The results revealed that fatal and serious accident cases significantly contribute to the increase in road traffic accident-related deaths, while minor accidents have an inverse relationship with mortality outcomes. These findings underscore the importance of differentiating between accident severity when analyzing road safety data and designing interventions.

Consequently, the study recommends targeted actions by government and stakeholders, including the enforcement of stricter traffic regulations, enhanced driver training and education, robust data collection systems, and improved road infrastructure and emergency response services. These interventions are critical to mitigating the fatal consequences of road accidents and enhancing public safety in Benue State.

Ultimately, this study provides empirical evidence and methodological guidance for traffic safety analysts and policymakers, demonstrating the utility of advanced count data models in capturing the dynamics of road traffic fatalities. It also lays a foundation for future research that could incorporate spatial, temporal, or behavioural variables to deepen the understanding of accident causality in Nigeria and similar contexts.

REFERENCES

- Akinyemi, L. O., & Asiyanbi, A. P. (2015). A statistical modeling of road traffic accidents in Lagos state, Nigeria. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 7(5), 345-352.
- Atubi, A. O. (2012). A spatio-temporal analysis of road traffic accident fatalities in Nigeria: Safety implications. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(6), 225-233.
- Eze, B. O., & Nwankwo, M. C. (2017). Analysis of road traffic accidents in Enugu State using Negative Binomial regression. *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, 36(2), 489-496.
- Federal Road Safety Corps. (2022). *Annual Road Traffic Crash Reports for Nigeria (2000–2022)*. FRSC Headquarters, Abuja.

- Gkritza, K., Moomen, M., & Mannering, F. L. (2010). Exploring the relationship between seatbelt usage and accident injury severity in a mature driver population. *Journal of Safety Research*, 41(3), 273-281.
- Hilbe, J. M. (2011). *Negative binomial regression* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Karlaftis, M. G., & Tarko, A. P. (1998). Heterogeneity considerations in accident modeling. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 30(4), 425-433.
- Lord, D., & Mannering, F. (2010). The statistical analysis of crash-frequency data: A review and assessment of methodological alternatives. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 44(5), 291-305.
- Miaou, S. P., & Lord, D. (2003). Modeling traffic crash-flow relationships for intersections: Dispersion parameter, functional form, and Bayes versus empirical Bayes methods. *Transportation Research Record*, 1840, 31-40.
- Njeru, R. W., & Ogalo, J. M. (2016). Statistical modeling of road accident injuries: Case of Nairobi County, Kenya. *Open Journal of Statistics*, 6, 1002-1013.
- Nwankwo, C. H. & Nwaigwe, G. I. (2016). A statistical model of road traffic crashes data in Anambra state, Nigeria: a Poisson regression approach. *European Journal of Statistics and Probability*, 1, 41-60.
- Ogundele, O. J., Ifeoma, C. I., & Ibitoye, A. O. (2016). Road traffic crashes in Nigeria: Issues and challenges. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 7(6), 396-403.
- Ojo, J. A., Ayinde, K., & Olatayo, T. O. (2020). Modeling of road traffic accident data using Poisson and Negative Binomial regression models: The case of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e05029.
- Oyekanmi, A. E., Oyatoye, E. O., & Alayande, A. O. (2019). Modeling road traffic accidents using Poisson and Zero-inflated Poisson regression models: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of the Nigerian Statistical Association*, 31(1), 35-52.
- Sadia, F. (2013). Performance of generalized poisson regression model and negative binomial regression model in the case of over-dispersion. *Count Data*, 12(1), 558-563.
- Savolainen, P. T., Mannering, F. L., Lord, D., & Quddus, M. A. (2011). The statistical analysis of highway crash-injury severities: A review and assessment of methodological alternatives. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 43(5), 1666-1676.
- Sharma, B. R., Singh, H., Gupta, M., & Sharma, A. (2013). Modeling road traffic accidents using count data regression models: A case study of Patiala city, India. *International Journal of Injury Control and Safety Promotion*, 20(3), 231-239.
- Shankar, V., Milton, J., & Mannering, F. (1997). Modeling accident frequencies as zero-altered probability processes: An empirical inquiry. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 29(6), 829-837.
- Wang, W. R. & Famoye, F. (1997). Modeling household fertility decisions with generalized poisson regression. *Journal of Population Economics*, 10, 273-283.

- Washington, S. P., Karlaftis, M. G., Mannering, F., & Anastasopoulos, P. C. (2020). *Statistical and econometric methods for transportation data analysis* (3rd ed.). CRC Press.
- World Health Organization. (2023). Global status report on road safety 2023. Geneva: WHO. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240064003>
- Zhang, Y., Yau, K. K., & Zhang, X. (2013). Analyzing the impact of weather conditions on accident severity using zero-inflated ordered probit model. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 59, 216-226.